

Using Molecular Models to Improve Students' Conceptual Understanding and Perception of Balancing Chemical Equations

Sheilla Twumwaah

Science Department, Odorgonno Senior High School, Accra, Ghana

Moses Abdullai Abukari

Department of Science Education, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Navrongo, Ghana

Philip Dorsah

Department of Science Education, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Navrongo, Ghana

Fatao Abudu

Department of Science Education, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Navrongo, Ghana

Abstract

This study examined the effect of molecular model kits on senior high school students' conceptual understanding and perceptions of balancing chemical equations. A quasi-experimental design was employed, involving an experimental group instructed using molecular model kits and a control group taught through conventional instructional methods. Pre- and post-tests were administered to assess students' conceptual understanding and perceptions of balancing chemical equations. Independent samples t-tests revealed no significant difference between the groups on pre-test scores, confirming baseline equivalence. However, post-test results revealed that students in the experimental group ($M = 20.26$, $SD = 6.36$) performed significantly better than those in the control group ($M = 18.70$, $SD = 5.44$), $t(58) = 2.37$, $p = .012$, indicating a statistically significant positive effect of molecular model use on conceptual understanding. Similarly, students in the experimental group reported significantly more positive perceptions ($M = 3.10$, $SD = 0.54$) than those in the control group ($M = 2.70$, $SD = 0.45$), $t(58) = 1.69$, $p = .045$. These findings suggest that molecular model kits enhance students' understanding and engagement by supporting meaningful connections among the macroscopic, microscopic, and symbolic representations of chemical phenomena. The study highlights the pedagogical value of incorporating visual and tactile instructional strategies in chemistry education to promote conceptual understanding and positive learner perceptions.

Keywords: *molecular models, chemical equations, conceptual understanding, student perception, chemistry education.*

Suggested citation: Twumwaah, S., Abukari, M.A., Dorsah, P., & Abudu, F. (2026). Using Molecular Models to Improve Students' Conceptual Understanding and Perception of Balancing Chemical Equations. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 4(2), 114-139. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2026.4(2).10

Introduction

The use of multiple representations is a core scientific practice across all scientific disciplines and is particularly essential in science education for supporting learners' understanding of abstract concepts. Representations enhance perceptual accessibility and provide tools for conceptualizing and communicating scientific phenomena (Ainsworth, 2006). In chemistry education, representations such as chemical equations, molecular diagrams, and physical molecular models enable learners to make sense of processes that are not directly observable, such as atomic rearrangements during chemical reactions (Gilbert & Treagust, 2009). Consequently, effective chemistry learning requires students to develop the ability to interpret and translate among different representational forms and to use them appropriately when constructing explanations and justifying claims (National Research Council, 2000).

Despite their pedagogical importance, research consistently shows that students at various educational levels experience difficulties in using and coordinating chemical representations. These challenges are particularly evident when students are required to move between macroscopic observations, sub-microscopic explanations, and symbolic representations such as chemical equations (Ainsworth, 2006; Rau, 2015). Chemistry is inherently abstract, and many of its concepts are best understood through hands-on or experiential learning activities that support visualization and model construction (Gilbert & Treagust, 2009). One area where students face persistent difficulties is in understanding chemical reactions and their symbolic representation, especially during introductory chemistry instruction (du Toit, 2016).

Chemical reactions can be represented using multiple forms, including word equations, symbolic equations, sub-microscopic particle representations, macroscopic observations, and diagrammatic or model-based representations. Word equations describe chemical changes using everyday language, while symbolic equations employ chemical symbols and formulas to express the conservation of matter. Sub-microscopic representations depict the behavior and interactions of atoms, ions, or molecules that lead to the formation of new substances, whereas diagrammatic representations rely on two-dimensional or three-dimensional models to visualize molecular structures (Gilbert & Treagust, 2009). Difficulties in coordinating these representational levels often result in misconceptions and hinder students' conceptual understanding of chemical reactions (Rau, 2015).

One instructional approach that has shown promise in addressing these challenges is the use of molecular models. Molecular models are concrete instructional tools that allow students to construct and visualize molecules using color-coded components that represent different atoms and bonds. These models support students in developing mental images of molecular structures and bonding relationships, thereby strengthening their understanding of abstract chemical concepts (Taskin & Bernholt,

2014). Among the various types of molecular models, ball-and-stick models are widely used in chemistry education because they clearly illustrate atomic connectivity and bond relationships, with atoms represented as spheres and bonds depicted as sticks (Gilbert & Treagust, 2009)

The use of molecular models promotes active learning by engaging students in hands-on manipulation of chemical representations, which enhances spatial reasoning and visualization skills. Research has shown that many students perceive chemistry as difficult due to challenges in linking molecular formulas, three-dimensional structures, and chemical properties (Cooper et al., 2013; Taskin & Bernholt, 2014). By providing a tangible bridge between symbolic equations and sub-microscopic processes, molecular models can help students better understand fundamental concepts such as balancing chemical equations, which require an appreciation of atom conservation and molecular rearrangement during chemical reactions.

Statement of the Problem

Chemistry is a discipline characterized by inherent abstractness and complexity, as it explains observable phenomena in terms of particles and processes that cannot be directly observed (Johnstone, 2000). According to Johnstone's representational framework, meaningful learning in chemistry requires the coordinated use of macroscopic, sub-microscopic, and symbolic representations, such as observable changes, molecular interactions, and chemical equations. However, research indicates that students often struggle to integrate these levels effectively during problem-solving.

Studies on chemical equations illustrate this challenge clearly. For instance, Hamerská et al. (2024) reported that students' ability to balance chemical equations frequently remains limited due to an overreliance on symbolic manipulation without strong conceptual links to sub-microscopic processes. This procedural emphasis tends to hinder a deep understanding of the chemical reactions involved. Evidence from intervention studies further suggests that instructional approaches that explicitly integrate sub-microscopic representations with symbolic manipulation can significantly enhance students' conceptual understanding and learning outcomes.

Despite these research insights, many chemistry classrooms continue to prioritize procedural strategies over integrative representational practices. As a result, learners often acquire superficial skills in balancing chemical equations and demonstrate weak conceptual understanding of the underlying chemical processes. Against this backdrop, the present study investigates the effect of using molecular model kits on senior high school students' conceptual understanding and perceptions of balancing chemical equations.

Research Questions

1. What effect does the use of molecular models have on students' conceptual understanding of balancing chemical equations?
2. What effect does the use of molecular models have on students' perceptions of balancing chemical equations?

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored in Johnstone's Chemistry Triplet, a foundational theory in chemical education asserting that understanding chemistry involves operating across three representational domains: macroscopic, sub-microscopic, and symbolic

representations. According to Johnstone's model, meaningful chemistry learning requires learners to interpret and integrate phenomena observable at the human scale, conceptual explanations at the particulate level, and representations such as chemical formulas and equations (Taber, 2013).

The macroscopic level encompasses observable chemical properties and changes, such as colour changes, gas evolution, and temperature variations during reactions. The sub-microscopic level involves explanatory models based on atoms, ions, and molecules that are invisible to the unaided senses. The symbolic level includes chemical symbols, molecular formulas, equations, graphs, and mathematical expressions used to represent reactive processes and quantitative relationships (Taber, 2013; RSC, 2021).

Johnstone conceptualized these levels as the vertices of a triangle—often referred to as Johnstone's triangle or the chemistry triplet—to emphasize that each domain is distinct yet interdependent. Effective chemistry instruction requires learners to make cognitive shifts among these domains, a process that is often effortless for experts but significantly challenging for novice learners (Taber, 2013; RSC, 2021). Research in chemistry education suggests that novice learners frequently experience cognitive overload when required to coordinate multiple representations simultaneously. This overload can impede the development of deep conceptual understanding because learners may focus on surface features of symbolic representations without connecting them meaningfully to particulate explanations or observable phenomena (Taber, 2013).

Balancing chemical equations illustrates the complexity inherent in representational coordination. Students often demonstrate procedural proficiency in manipulating symbolic coefficients without robust conceptual understanding of the underlying particulate processes—such as conservation of atoms or molecular rearrangements—that the equations represent. A recent empirical study found that students' reliance on symbolic representations alone, without effective linkage to sub-microscopic reasoning, hindered true conceptual understanding of chemical equations (Hamerská et al., 2024).

Johnstone's representational framework has been widely applied to curriculum design and instructional strategies in chemistry education. It provides a lens through which researchers and educators can diagnose learning difficulties and design interventions that support transitions among representational domains (Taber, 2013).

In this study, molecular models serve as instructional tools that make sub-microscopic entities visible and tangible, thereby supporting translational competence, the ability to move fluently between representations. By providing a concrete bridge between symbolic equations and particulate processes, molecular models can help learners integrate representational domains more effectively. This theoretical grounding justifies the use of molecular models to enhance students' conceptual understanding and perceptions of balancing chemical equations, as explored in this research.

Relationship Between Johnstone's Levels of Representation

Chemical phenomena can be explained through three interconnected levels of representation: macroscopic, sub-microscopic, and symbolic (Talanquer, 2011; Taber, 2013). These levels are often depicted as the vertices of a triangle, commonly referred to as Johnstone's Triangle, to illustrate that each domain provides a unique lens through which chemical ideas can be understood and that meaningful learning requires movement among all three (Taber, 2013). The three representations are not isolated;

rather, they operate together to support learners in conceptualizing abstract chemical systems and making sense of observable phenomena.

At the macroscopic level, chemical phenomena are described in terms of observable properties and changes, such as colour changes, gas evolution, and temperature variations during a reaction. The sub-microscopic level involves molecular and atomic explanations that cannot be directly observed, and the symbolic level uses chemical symbols, formulas, equations, graphs, and other notation to represent and quantify chemical processes (Taber, 2013; Talanquer, 2011). Together, these representational domains provide complementary perspectives that enhance learners' abilities to describe, explain, and predict chemical behaviour.

Although these three levels are essential for understanding chemistry, students often find it difficult to coordinate among them. Common learning difficulties include over-reliance on symbolic manipulation without understanding underlying particulate processes, weak connections between observable phenomena and molecular explanations, and limited experience relating symbolic conventions to real chemical behaviour (Taber, 2013; Rau, 2015). These challenges reflect the cognitive demands of moving between different representational modes and indicate that students often lack the translational skills needed to navigate the triplet effectively. That is, the ability to translate meaningfully from one representational level to another.

The capacity to move fluently among macroscopic, sub-microscopic, and symbolic representations, often called translational competence, is fundamental to developing deep conceptual understanding in chemistry (Taber, 2013). Without this competence, learners may develop fragmented ideas or misconceptions because they fail to link what they see in the laboratory with particulate explanations or symbolic representations of reactions.

Figure 1. Johnstone's Triangle (Johnstone, 1982, 1991). Proposes that Chemistry be Viewed and Taught on Three Interrelated Levels—the Macroscopic Level, the Symbolic Level, and the Submicroscopic Level

Source: Schmidt, 2021

Representational models and tools, such as tactile molecular structures or particulate drawings, can provide cognitive support by making invisible sub-microscopic processes more concrete and facilitating connections across representation levels. For example, when students construct or interpret molecular models, they are better able to visualize how atoms and molecules reorganize during a chemical reaction, enhancing their ability not only to describe observable changes but also to express those changes symbolically (Hamerská et al., 2024; Taber, 2013). This interplay among levels is what makes a representational approach powerful for both teaching and learning chemistry.

Johnstone's theoretical framework suggests that knowledge of chemistry is best achieved when learners can relate macroscopic observations to sub-microscopic explanations and represent both through symbolic expressions such as balanced chemical equations (Taber, 2013). Instruction that explicitly reinforces these links through multiple representations can strengthen learners' conceptual understanding and improve their ability to solve problems that require integrated thinking across representational domains.

Attitudes of Students Toward Balancing Chemical Equations

Many students perceive chemistry in general, and symbolic aspects such as chemical formulas and equations in particular, as difficult or intimidating. Studies of attitudes toward chemistry report that learners often view chemistry as challenging and abstract, with symbolic representations and complex procedures contributing to anxiety and reduced motivation (Chang & Menke, 2022). Research further indicates that perceived difficulty plays a significant role in shaping students' attitudes. When learners find content hard to understand or irrelevant to real life, they tend to become disengaged and less motivated to learn (Musengimana et al., 2021).

Developing positive attitudes toward chemistry is important because attitude influences students' willingness to engage deeply with content and persist through complex tasks such as balancing equations. Students with positive attitudes are more likely to invest effort, use varied learning strategies, and perform better academically compared to those with negative attitudes (Musengimana et al., 2021). In the context of balancing chemical equations specifically, instructional approaches that help students understand underlying concepts can positively influence attitudes. When teaching supports meaningful engagement and helps learners connect abstract symbolic representations with concrete reasoning, students are more likely to develop both improved understanding and more favourable attitudes toward these challenging chemistry tasks.

Alternative Conceptions in Chemistry Learning

Students' alternative conceptions in chemistry arise when their existing mental models conflict with scientifically accepted explanations. Research in chemistry education consistently shows that learners often construct internal representations of chemical phenomena that differ from the canonical scientific model, particularly for topics involving abstract, invisible entities such as atoms, molecules, and ions (Rau, 2015; Taber, 2013). These internal representations, also called alternative conceptions or misconceptions, persist even after instruction unless instruction explicitly addresses them.

Alternative conceptions are strongly tied to the representational complexity of chemistry. Students frequently misinterpret macroscopic phenomena because they attribute properties of observable matter (solid, liquid, colour, texture) directly to

representations of atoms and molecules, rather than conceptualizing particulate behaviour at the sub-microscopic level (Gilbert & Treagust, 2009; Demircioğlu et al., 2005). For example, research has documented that learners may draw particles with inappropriate shapes or sizes or may reason that particles retain macroscopic properties such as solidity or colour, indicating confusion about the nature of particles and how they relate to observable changes (Ngai et al., 2014; Head et al., 2017).

The macroscopic–submicroscopic–symbolic representation levels framework provides insight into sources of alternative conceptions. When students fail to coordinate among these levels, they tend to rely on simplistic or surface-level explanations that are inconsistent with expert understanding. Students often struggle to relate symbolic representations like formulas and equations to particulate behaviour, or to explain how macroscopic observations reflect underlying particle interactions (Talanquer, 2011; Taber, 2013).

Chemistry education researchers emphasize that alternative conceptions are not merely errors in calculation or recall, but reflect deep-seated reasoning patterns that arise from learners' everyday experiences and cognitive frameworks. These ideas are typically resistant to instruction when teaching focuses on procedures rather than conceptual meaning (Rau, 2015; Taber, 2013). Challenging alternative conceptions therefore, requires pedagogical strategies that engage learners in meaningful conceptual change. In conceptual change, existing mental models are confronted, examined, and restructured in light of scientifically accepted explanations (Head et al., 2017; Taber, 2013).

Molecular Modelling in the Teaching of Chemistry

Molecular modelling plays an important role in chemistry education by providing learners with tools to visualise and interact with representations of molecules, which are otherwise imperceptible to the human senses. Because chemistry involves three-dimensional structures, spatial relationships, and abstract concepts such as bonding and molecular geometry, models help reduce cognitive load and make these abstract ideas more accessible to learners (Royal Society of Chemistry Education, 2016; Royal Society of Chemistry, 2019). Physical molecular models, such as ball-and-stick kits, allow students to construct tangible representations of molecules. These models illustrate atomic connectivity, approximate bond angles, and spatial arrangement, enabling students to develop mental images that enhance their understanding of structure and bonding.

Digital molecular modelling, including computer simulations and visualisations, extends this support by enabling learners to explore molecules in interactive environments, often with the ability to manipulate structures and observe dynamic behaviour (Aksela & Lundell, 2008). Studies in chemistry education have shown that using molecular models as instructional tools can improve students' comprehension of complex concepts, particularly those involving three-dimensional structures and spatial reasoning.

Empirical Framework

Research in chemistry education has consistently shown that students' conceptual understanding improves when instruction incorporates multiple representations and active engagement with models, particularly for abstract topics such as stoichiometry and chemical equations. According to Taber (2013), students often struggle with abstract sub-microscopic concepts because they cannot easily connect symbolic

equations with particulate explanations and macroscopic observations. This challenge underscores the need for instructional strategies that make invisible processes visible and cognitively accessible to learners.

A growing body of empirical evidence supports the use of visual and interactive representations to strengthen chemistry learning. Rau (2015) reported that instructional approaches that help students make connections among graphical and representational formats significantly enhance understanding of complex chemical concepts. In a study integrating computer simulations into stoichiometry instruction, students who used interactive simulations achieved notably higher post-test performance and retained conceptual understanding longer than control groups, suggesting that dynamic visualisation supports meaningful learning in abstract domains (Swafford et al., 2016).

Similarly, research by Taber (2013) and Talanquer (2011) highlights that tools enabling learners to construct and interpret multiple representational forms, such as particulate diagrams and molecular models, can improve students' representational competence and conceptual understanding. These tools help learners recognise how symbolic equations relate to underlying chemical processes, thereby reducing misconceptions and enhancing confidence.

Studies focusing specifically on manipulative models provide further empirical support for the pedagogical value of modelling. For example, Shultz and Stears (1996) found that students using physical manipulatives to explore conservation of mass and matter developed stronger conceptual reasoning and were better able to balance chemical equations compared to those taught with traditional lecture methods. Manipulatives enabled learners to visualise balanced equations and articulate the law of conservation of matter in their own words, reflecting deeper understanding.

Research into coloured block manipulatives also demonstrates instructional benefit. When students used coloured blocks to represent different atom types during balancing activities, their post-test scores improved significantly relative to students receiving conventional instruction. Furthermore, students reported increased interest and engagement, indicating that physical modelling can make chemistry learning more approachable and meaningful.

Beyond physical models, studies exploring student-generated representations have shown that constructing animations or diagrams fosters deep conceptual shifts. For instance, Bodner and Herron (2002) demonstrated that students who created their own particulate animations improved their ability to interpret and communicate chemical phenomena, suggesting that learner-generated representations can promote reflective understanding and meta-cognitive growth.

Similarly, Cooper and Klymkowsky (2013) investigated the impact of learner-constructed sub-microscopic diagrams on stoichiometric problem solving. Students who engaged in constructing detailed sub-micro representations performed better in solving stoichiometry tasks and more accurately identified and corrected their own misconceptions.

Methodology

Design

This study adopted a positivist paradigm and employed a quantitative research approach. The positivist perspective is based on the assumption that social reality exists

independently of human perception and can be investigated objectively through systematic observation and empirical evidence (Muijs, 2011). Within this framework, knowledge is derived from experience and can be analyzed using measurable and statistical data. The researcher's role under positivism is to maintain objectivity and minimize personal bias or participant influence throughout the research process. In line with this tradition, quantitative research seeks to explain phenomena by collecting numerical data and performing statistical analyses to test hypotheses and establish relationships between variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

The study employed a quasi-experimental design, specifically the pre-test post-test non-equivalent control group design. Quasi-experimental designs are often used when random allocation of participants is not feasible, particularly in naturalistic settings such as classrooms (Muijs, 2011). The experimental group in this study received instruction using molecular models, while the control group received traditional instruction. The design is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Study Design

Group	Pre-Test Instruments	Intervention	Post-Test Instruments
Experimental	<i>BCECT, BCEPQ</i>	<i>Teaching using molecular models</i>	<i>BCECT, BCEPQ</i>
Control	<i>BCECT, BCEPQ</i>	<i>Traditional teaching approach</i>	<i>BCECT, BCEPQ</i>

Sample and Sampling Procedure

The study comprised 60 Form Two Chemistry students selected from two Senior High Schools in the Greater Accra Region of Ghana. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select schools that offered the General Science programme and had comparable academic structures.

Following school selection, intact classes were used to avoid disruption to the normal instructional process. One intact class ($n = 30$) from the first school was assigned to the experimental group, while one intact class ($n = 30$) from the second school constituted the control group. The experimental group received instruction using molecular models as a hands-on teaching intervention, whereas the control group was taught using the traditional lecture-based method.

To enhance internal validity and reduce selection bias, efforts were made to ensure comparability between the two groups. This was achieved by examining students' prior academic performance in Chemistry, age distribution, and relevant demographic characteristics. Pre-intervention equivalence was further considered to ensure that any observed differences in post-intervention performance could reasonably be attributed to the instructional strategy rather than pre-existing differences.

Instruments

Data were collected using the Balancing Chemical Equations Concept Test (BCECT) and the Balancing Chemical Equations Perception Questionnaire (BCEPQ). The BCECT was developed to assess students' conceptual understanding and procedural skills related to balancing chemical equations [see Appendix 2]. The instrument was administered as both a pre-test and a post-test to measure learning gains following instruction.

The BCECT consists of two sections. Section A comprises 10 items assessing students' conceptual understanding of chemical equations, including definitions, symbols,

governing principles, and the identification of correctly balanced equations. These items are primarily multiple-choice and short-response in nature. Section B contains 10 structured items that require students to balance chemical equations, assessing procedural competence across a range of reaction types.

Section A items were scored dichotomously, with 2 points awarded for each correct response, while Section B items were awarded 2 points for each correctly balanced equation. The maximum obtainable score on the BCECT was therefore 40 points. Higher scores indicate greater conceptual understanding and proficiency in balancing chemical equations.

The BCEPQ was designed to measure students' perceptions of balancing chemical equations. It comprises 18 items rated on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from Strongly Agree (5) to Strongly Disagree (1) [see Appendix 1]. The instrument consisted of five factors: value of chemical equations, interest/enjoyment, perceived competence, anxiety, and gender stereotypes. The value of chemical equations captures students' perceptions of the importance, usefulness, and societal relevance of chemical equations. Items assess the extent to which students view balancing chemical equations as valuable beyond the classroom, relevant to everyday life, and essential for chemistry learners.

The interest/enjoyment factor reflects students' affective engagement and intrinsic motivation toward balancing chemical equations. Items probe whether students find the topic interesting, enjoyable, or appealing. This factor represents the emotional appeal of the task and students' willingness to engage with balancing chemical equations. Higher scores indicate greater interest and enjoyment, while negatively phrased items were reverse-coded.

Perceived competence measures students' beliefs about their ability and preparedness to successfully balance chemical equations. The factor aligns with self-efficacy theory and reflects students' judgments of their competence rather than their actual performance.

The anxiety factor assesses students' negative emotional reactions, such as fear, nervousness, and anxiety, associated with balancing chemical equations. Items capture affective responses that may hinder engagement and learning. Gender stereotypes factor represents students' gender-related beliefs and stereotypes concerning ability in balancing chemical equations. Items examine perceptions that the task is more suited to males or that males perform better than females.

Negatively worded items were reverse-scored so that higher scores consistently reflected more positive perceptions.

Table 2. Dimensions and Items of the BCEPQ

s/n	Dimension/factor	No. of items	Items
1	Value of chemical equations	4	1, 2,3,4
2	Interest/enjoyment	3	5, 6, 7
3	Perceived competence	4	8, 9, 10, 11
4	Anxiety	3	12, 13, 14
5	Gender stereotypes	4	15, 16, 17, 18

Validity and Reliability

The validity of the Balancing Chemical Equations Concept Test (BCECT) and the Balancing Chemical Equations Perception Questionnaire (BCEPQ) was established through expert review, where supervisors and experienced chemistry teachers evaluated the test items for both face and content validity. This ensured that the items were relevant, clear, and adequately represented the construct of conceptual understanding in balancing chemical equations. The reliability of the BCEPQ was assessed using the Cronbach alpha coefficient, which yielded a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.77, indicating that the internal consistency of the instrument is acceptable.

Data Collection Procedure

Before data collection, permission was obtained from the headmaster of the participating school through an introductory letter from the Department of Science Education, School of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education. The purpose and scope of the study were clearly explained to all participants. Initially, pre-tests were administered to both the experimental and control groups using the BCECT and BCEPQ to establish baseline equivalence in terms of conceptual understanding and perceptions regarding chemical equations. Following the pre-test, the intervention was implemented exclusively with the experimental group for four weeks, during which students were taught to balance chemical equations using molecular models. Meanwhile, the control group continued to receive instruction using the traditional teaching approach. At the end of the intervention, post-tests were conducted for both groups using the same instruments to evaluate changes in conceptual understanding and perceptions of balancing chemical equations.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and frequencies, were used to summarize students' performance perception scores in pre-tests and post-tests. Independent samples t-tests were used to compare mean scores between the experimental and control groups, and to assess the effect of the intervention on students' performance and perceptions regarding balancing chemical equations. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 27 and GraphPad Prism 8.0.1.

Test of Normality

Normality of post-test perception and performance scores was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Results indicated that the perception scores were approximately normally distributed for both the control group ($W = 0.967, p = 0.469$) and the experimental group ($W = 0.951, p = 0.180$). Similarly, the performance scores were consistent with normality for the control group ($W = 0.973, p = 0.636$) and the experimental group ($W = 0.944, p = 0.122$). Again, visual inspection of Q–Q plots for both measures further confirmed that the data points closely followed the diagonal reference line, supporting the assumption of approximate normality (Ghasemi & Zahediasl, 2012). Table 3 presents the Shapiro–Wilk Test for Normality of Post-Test Perception and Performance Scores.

Table 3. Shapiro–Wilk Test for Normality of Post-Test Perception and Performance Scores

Measure	Group	<i>W</i>	p-value
Perception	CG	0.9673	0.4691
	EG	0.951	0.1796
Performance	CG	0.973	0.636
	EG	0.944	0.122

Figure 2 presents the normal Q–Q plot of the post-test performance scores for the control group (CG) and experimental group (EG). Figure 3 presents the normal Q–Q plot of the post-test perception scores of the control group and experimental group.

Figure 2. Normal Q–Q Plot of the Post-Test Performance Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Figure 3. Normal Q–Q Plot of the Post-Test Perception Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Ethical Considerations

Ethical protocols were strictly adhered to throughout the study. Permission was first obtained from the headmasters of the participating schools before data collection commenced. Informed consent was sought from all student participants. The purpose of the study was clearly explained, and students were assured of confidentiality and

anonymity. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and students were informed of their right to withdraw at any time.

Implementation of the Intervention

Chemical models are essential tools for facilitating students' understanding of the abstract nature of chemistry. While such models play a critical role in the learning process, they also present significant cognitive demands for many learners, as students must interpret abstract representations and connect them to observable phenomena (Taskin et al., 2015). In chemistry, many processes at the atomic or molecular level are not directly observable, requiring students to work with symbolic and abstract representations to construct mental models of the sub-microscopic world. These visualizations bridge the gap between visible experimental outcomes and the invisible atomic or molecular processes, supporting deeper conceptual understanding.

Gilbert (2008) identifies three key competencies for working effectively with chemical representations: (1) understanding the conventional rules and symbols associated with chemical representations, (2) the ability to accurately draw or construct representations of chemical processes, and (3) the capacity to translate between different forms of representation, such as converting symbolic equations into molecular models or diagrams (Taskin et al., 2015).

In this study, the intervention involved the use of molecular model kits to teach students how to balance chemical equations. These kits consist of colored balls representing atomic nuclei, each with holes to accommodate connecting pegs symbolizing chemical bonds. The color coding differentiates elements, while the number of holes corresponds to the typical valency of the atom. The kit was selected to include a representative set of elements relevant to the instructional objectives, rather than all possible atoms. Table 4 presents the color code and valence of the atoms used in the intervention.

Table 4. The Color Code and Valency of the Atoms Used in the Intervention

Colour of Ball	Number of Holes	Atom Represented
Black	4	Carbon
White	1	Hydrogen
Red	2	Oxygen
Blue	3	Nitrogen
Green	1	Chlorine
Orange	1	Iodine/Bromine

By manipulating these hands-on, practical models, students were able to visualize molecular structures, understand the stoichiometry of chemical reactions, and translate symbolic chemical equations into tangible, three-dimensional forms. This approach provided a concrete, interactive means for students to engage with abstract chemical concepts, fostering both conceptual understanding and positive perceptions of balancing chemical equations. The color code and corresponding atoms used in the intervention are summarized in Table 5. Table 6 presents the color code of the models and atoms.

Table 5. Color Code of Balls and Atoms Represented

Color of Ball	Atom Represented	Chemical Symbol
White	Hydrogen	H

Black	Carbon	C
Red	Oxygen	O
Green	Halogens (Fluorine, Chlorine, Bromine, Iodine)	F, Cl, Br, I
Blue	Nitrogen	N
Orange	Sodium	Na
Yellow	Sulfur	S

Table 6. Color Code of Models and Atoms Represented

Model	Color	Atom
	White	Hydrogen (H)
	Black	Carbon (C)
	Red	Oxygen (O)
	Green	Halogen (F, Cl, Br, I)
	Blue	Nitrogen (N)
	Orange	Sodium (Na)
	Yellow	Sulphur (S)

By manipulating these hands-on, practical models, students were able to visualize molecular structures, understand the stoichiometry of chemical reactions, and translate symbolic chemical equations into tangible, three-dimensional forms. This approach provided a concrete, interactive means for students to engage with abstract chemical concepts, fostering both conceptual understanding and positive perceptions of balancing chemical equations. In the intervention, molecular model kits were used to provide students with visual and tactile representations of atoms and molecules. This allows them to see and manipulate the components of chemical reactions. The process involved the following steps:

Representation of Reactants and Products

Students first constructed models representing the reactants in a chemical equation. For example, in $\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}$, students built separate models of two hydrogen molecules (H_2) and one oxygen molecule (O_2). For products, they constructed the water molecules using the same atomic components. This step helped students visualize the actual atoms involved and recognize the need to conserve atoms across reactants and products.

Counting Atoms and Identifying Imbalances

Students were guided to count the number of each type of atom in the reactants and compare it with the number in the products. Using molecular models, it becomes immediately apparent if a reaction is unbalanced. For example, in $\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}$, students would notice 2 oxygen atoms in the reactants but only 1 oxygen atom in the product.

Adjusting Molecules Using Models

To balance the equation, students added additional molecules using the models. For $\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}$, they would add another H_2O molecule to match the oxygen atoms, and then adjust the number of hydrogen molecules accordingly. Physically moving the molecular models allows students to experiment with coefficients until all atoms are balanced.

Translating the Model Back to the Symbolic Equation

Once the models reflected an equal number of atoms on both sides of the reaction, students recorded the balanced equation symbolically. For $\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}$, after adjusting, the model shows two water molecules and four hydrogen atoms, leading to the balanced equation: $2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Reinforcement and Practice with Multiple Examples

The intervention included multiple reaction types: combination ($\text{C} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2$), synthesis ($\text{C} + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$), single displacement ($\text{Na} + \text{Cl}_2 \rightarrow \text{NaCl}$), and more complex reactions ($\text{CH}_4 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$). By repeatedly constructing models, counting atoms, and adjusting molecules, students strengthened their mental models of atom conservation, making the balancing process more intuitive. Table 7 presents example equations used in the intervention. Table 8 presents molecular model diagrams of the chemical equations.

Table 7. Example Equations Used in the Intervention

Example	Unbalanced Equation	Balanced Equation
1	$\text{C} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2$	$\text{C} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2$
2	$\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
3	$\text{C} + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$	$\text{C} + 2\text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$
4	$\text{Na} + \text{Cl}_2 \rightarrow \text{NaCl}$	$2\text{Na} + \text{Cl}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{NaCl}$
5	$\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{NH}_3$	$\text{N}_2 + 3\text{H}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{NH}_3$
6	$\text{CH}_4 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{CH}_4 + 2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
7	$\text{N}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	$2\text{N}_2 + 5\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$

Table 8. Equations and Their Molecular Model Diagrams

Equation	Molecular model diagram
$\text{C} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2$ (balanced)	
$\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (unbalanced)	

$2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (balanced)	
$\text{C} + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$ (Unbalanced)	
$\text{C} + 2\text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$ (balanced)	
$\text{Na} + \text{Cl}_2 \rightarrow \text{NaCl}$ (Unbalanced)	
$2\text{Na} + \text{Cl}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{NaCl}$ (balanced)	
$\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{NH}_3$ (unbalanced)	
$\text{N}_2 + 3\text{H}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{NH}_3$ (Balanced)	

Results and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Participants were 60 students drawn from comparable classes and assigned to either a control group ($n = 30$) or an experimental group ($n = 30$). The control group consisted of 15 females (50.0%) and 15 males (50.0%), while the experimental group included 17 females (56.7%) and 13 males (43.3%). In both groups, the majority of students were aged 16–20 years (86.7%), with a smaller proportion aged 13–15 years (13.3%). The control and experimental groups were comparable in terms of sex and age distribution. Table 9 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Table 9. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Control Group ($n = 30$)		Experimental Group ($n = 30$)	
		<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Sex	Female	15	50	17	56.7
	Male	15	50	13	43.3
Age	13–15	4	13.3	4	13.3
	16–20	26	86.7	26	86.7

Effect of Molecular Models on Students' Conceptual Understanding

Table 10 presents the independent samples t-test for the pre-test scores of the experimental and control groups. The analysis aimed to determine whether there was a significant difference in students' conceptual understanding before the intervention.

Table 10. Independent Samples t-Test Results for the Pre-Test Scores

Group	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Experimental	30	12.46	4.34	0.000	58	1.00
Control	30	12.13	4.20			

The pre-test scores of the experimental group ($M = 12.46$, $SD = 4.34$) and the control group ($M = 12.13$, $SD = 4.20$) did not differ significantly, $t(58) = 0.000$, $p = 1.000$. This indicates that both groups had comparable levels of conceptual understanding before the introduction of molecular models, confirming the equivalence of the groups at baseline.

Table 11 presents the independent samples t-test for the post-test scores of the experimental and control groups. This analysis was conducted to determine whether the use of molecular models significantly affected students' conceptual understanding.

Table 11. Independent Samples t-Test of the Post-Test Performance Scores

Group	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Experimental	30	20.26	6.36	2.370	58	0.012
Control	30	18.70	5.44			

The results show that the experimental group ($M = 20.26$, $SD = 6.36$) scored significantly higher than the control group ($M = 18.70$, $SD = 5.44$) on the post-test, $t(58) = 2.370$, $p = 0.012$. This indicates that the use of molecular models had a positive and statistically significant effect on students' conceptual understanding. The results suggest that students who engaged with molecular models achieved better learning outcomes compared to those who were taught without such models.

Similarly, Ridzuan and Iksan (2017) investigated the effectiveness of using coloured blocks to teach the concept of balancing chemical equations. They found a significant difference between the control and treatment groups on their post-test scores. Students who used coloured blocks demonstrated greater development in their post-test performance compared to those taught using conventional methods. Additionally, students showed increased interest in chemistry when the concept of balancing chemical equations was taught using coloured blocks (Ridzuan & Iksan, 2017).

Wu et al. (2000) also examined the use of visualization tools to promote conceptual understanding of chemical representations. They reported that the eChem tool helped students construct models and translate between representations (Wu et al., 2000).

Effect of Molecular Models on Students' Perception of Balancing Chemical Equations

Table 12 presents the independent samples t-test results for the pre-test scores of students' perception toward balancing chemical equations. The analysis was conducted

to determine whether there was a significant difference between the experimental and control groups before the intervention.

Table 12. Independent Samples t-Test of the Pre-Test Perception Scores

Group	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Experimental	30	2.74	0.32	-0.709	58	.40
Control	30	2.81	0.38			

It was found that the pre-test perception scores of the experimental group ($M = 2.74$, $SD = 0.32$) and the control group ($M = 2.81$, $SD = 0.38$) did not differ significantly, $t(58) = -0.709$, $p = 0.40$. This indicates that both groups had comparable perceptions toward balancing chemical equations before the use of molecular models, confirming that any differences observed in the post-test can be attributed to the intervention. Table 13 presents the results of the independent samples t-test for the post-test scores of students' perception toward balancing chemical equations.

Table 13. Independent Samples t-Test of Post-Test Perception Scores

Group	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Experimental	30	3.10	0.54	1.690	58	.0045
Control	30	2.70	0.45			

The independent samples t-test results indicate a significant difference in perception between the experimental group ($M = 3.10$, $SD = 0.54$) and the control group ($M = 2.70$, $SD = 0.45$), $t(58) = 1.69$, $p = 0.045$. This suggests that students who were taught using molecular models developed a more positive perception of balancing chemical equations compared to students who received conventional instruction. The improvement in perception implies that the intervention not only enhanced conceptual understanding but also positively influenced students' attitudes toward the learning task.

These results are consistent with prior research that manipulative and visualization tools in chemistry improve both comprehension and engagement. For instance, Ridzuan and Iksan (2017) reported that students using coloured blocks to balance chemical equations showed significant post-test improvement and increased interest in chemistry concepts. Similarly, Wu et al. (2001) found that visualization tools promoted active construction of mental models, supporting both understanding and positive perceptions in chemistry learning. The findings suggest that molecular models are effective instructional tools that simultaneously foster conceptual understanding and positive student perceptions, reinforcing the value of hands-on and visual approaches in chemistry education.

Conclusion

This study investigated the use of molecular model kits as teaching and learning tools in the instruction of chemical equations to enhance senior high school students' ability to balance chemical reactions. The findings highlight the importance of engaging learners through visual and tactile instructional approaches, particularly when teaching abstract concepts in chemistry. Chemistry learning operates across three major levels

of representation: the macroscopic level, which involves observable changes; the sub-microscopic level, which involves the behavior of atoms and molecules; and the symbolic level, which involves chemical formulas and equations. While the macroscopic level is generally easier for students to grasp, the abstract nature of the sub-microscopic and symbolic levels poses significant learning challenges. This study addressed these challenges by employing molecular model kits to bridge the gap between the unseen molecular world and symbolic representations.

The intervention demonstrated that visual and tactile materials, such as molecular model kits, are effective in fostering students' conceptual understanding of chemical reactions. Molecular models enabled students to visualize particle interactions, comprehend the nature of chemical bonding, and develop a deeper understanding of the principles underlying the balancing of chemical equations. In addition, the instructional approach enhanced classroom interaction and student motivation, thereby promoting more active and meaningful learning. Overall, the study underscores the pedagogical value of incorporating innovative visual strategies to make abstract chemical concepts more accessible and comprehensible to learners.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the integration of molecular model kits into chemistry instruction may support students in visualizing chemical reactions and other abstract concepts more effectively. Instruction that explicitly links macroscopic and sub-microscopic representations may enhance students' ability to connect observable phenomena with the underlying particle-level explanations. Providing learners with multiple forms of representation, including sub-microscopic diagrams and symbolic equations, may strengthen their ability to translate between different levels of chemical understanding. The incorporation of hands-on, activity-based learning approaches may further promote student engagement, motivation, and deeper conceptual understanding of chemistry principles.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Ainsworth, S. (2006). DeFT: A conceptual framework for considering learning with multiple representations. *Learning and Instruction*, 16(3), 183–198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2006.03.001>
- Aksela, M., & Lundell, J. (2008). Computer-based molecular modelling: Finnish school teachers' experiences and views. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 9(4), 301–308. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B818464J>
- Behmke, D., Kerven, D., Lutz, R., Paredes, J., Pennington, R., Brannock, E., Deiters, M., & Rose, J. (2018). Augmented reality chemistry: Transforming 2-D molecular representations into interactive 3-D structures. *Proceedings of the Interdisciplinary STEM Teaching and Learning Conference*, 2(1), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.20429/stem.2018.020103>

- Bodner, G. M., & Herron, J. D. (2002). Problem-solving in chemistry. In J. K. Gilbert, O. De Jong, R. T. Justi, D. F. Treagust, & J. H. Van Driel (Eds.), *Chemical education: Towards research-based practice* (pp. 235–266). Kluwer Academic Publishers. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/George-Bodner/publication/226345872_Problem-Solving_in_Chemistry/links/0deec522787384698d000000/Problem-Solving-in-Chemistry.pdf
- Chang, J., & Menke, E. J. (2022). Measuring attitude toward chemistry, biology, and math at a Hispanic-serving institution. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 99(4), 1758–1765. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.1c01109>
- Cooper, M. M., & Klymkowsky, M. W. (2013). Chemistry, Life, the Universe, and Everything: A new approach to general chemistry, and a model for curriculum reform. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 90(9), 1116–1122. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ed300456y>
- Cooper, M. M., Corley, L. M., & Underwood, S. M. (2013). Investigation of college chemistry students' understanding of structure–property relationships. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 50(6), 699–721. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21093>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Demircioğlu, G., Ayas, A., & Demircioğlu, H. (2005). Conceptual change achieved through a new teaching program on acids and bases. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 6(1), 36–51. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B4RP90003K>
- Du Toit, A. (2016). Students' difficulties in understanding chemical reactions in introductory chemistry. *African Journal of Research in Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 20(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18117295.2016.1157983>
- Fraenkel, J. R., Wallen, N. E., & Hyun, H. H. (2019). *How to design and evaluate research in education* (10th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Ghasemi, A., & Zahediasl, S. (2012). Normality tests for statistical analysis: a guide for non-statisticians. *International journal of endocrinology and metabolism*, 10(2), 486–489. <https://doi.org/10.5812/ijem.3505>
- Gilbert, J. K., & Treagust, D. F. (Eds.). (2009). *Multiple representations in chemical education*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-8872-8>
- Hamerská, L., Matěcha, T., Tóthová, M., & Rusek, M. (2024). Between symbols and particles: Investigating the complexity of learning chemical equations. *Education Sciences*, 14(6), 570. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14060570>
- Hanson, R. (2017). Visualization and representation in chemistry education: The role of laboratory-based learning. *International Journal of Science Education*, 39(1), 1–17.
- Head, M. L., Yoder, K., Genton, E., & Sumperl, J. (2017). A quantitative method to determine preservice chemistry teachers' perceptions of chemical representations. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 18(5), 825–840. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7RP00109F>
- Heitzman, K., & Krajcik, J. (2005). Urban seventh-graders' translations of chemical equations. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 42(9), 975–993. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.20108>

Johnstone, A. H. (1982). Macro- and micro-chemistry. *School Science Reviews (Notes and Correspondence)*, 64(227), 377–379.

Johnstone, A. H. (1991). Why is science difficult to learn? Things are seldom what they seem. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 7, 75–83. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.1991.tb00230.x>

Johnstone, A. H. (2000). Teaching of chemistry: Logical or psychological? *Chemical Education Research and Practice in Europe*, 1(1), 9–15.

Luxford, C. J., & Bretz, S. L. (2014). Teaching and learning chemical bonding: Research-based evidence for misconceptions and conceptual difficulties experienced by students. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 19(2), 1253–1269. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RP00035B>

Muijs, D. (2011). *Doing quantitative research in education with SPSS* (2nd ed.). SAGE Publications.

Musengimana, J., Kampire, E., & Ntawiha, P. (2021). Factors affecting secondary schools students' attitudes toward learning chemistry: A review of literature. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 17(1), em1931. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/9379>

Ngai, S. C., Man, Y. B., & Gunstone, R. F. (2014). Students' competence in translating between different types of chemical representations. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 21(1), 119–136. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RP00301G>

Ogundiji, O. (2024). Diagnosis of students' difficulties in balancing chemical equations. *Journal of General Education and Humanities*, 3(4), 359–368. <https://doi.org/10.58421/gehu.v3i4.262>

Rahmawati, Y., Dianhar, H., & Arifin, F. (2021). Analysing students' spatial abilities in chemistry learning using 3D virtual representation. *Education Sciences*, 11(4), 185. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11040185>

Rau, M. A. (2015). Enhancing undergraduate chemistry learning by helping students make connections among multiple graphical representations. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 16(3), 654–669. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5RP00065C>

Ridzuan, A. A., & Iksan, Z. (2017). The effectiveness of using coloured blocks in teaching the concept of balancing chemical equations in chemistry. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 15(3), 567–583. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-016-9750-2>

Royal Society of Chemistry (2021). *Improve students' understanding with Johnstone's triangle*. RSC Education. <https://edu.rsc.org/feature/improve-students-understanding-with-johnstones-triangle/4019740.article>

Royal Society of Chemistry. (2016). The value of modelling molecules. <https://edu.rsc.org/education-research/the-value-of-modelling-molecules/2000365.article>

Royal Society of Chemistry. (2019). *Reasons to craft your own molecular models*. <https://edu.rsc.org/ideas/reasons-to-craft-your-own-molecular-models/3009984.article>

Royal Society of Chemistry. (2020). *Students' struggle with multiple representations in chemistry education*. <https://edu.rsc.org/education-research/students-struggle-with-multiple-representations/4011073.article>

Schmidt, S. J. (2021). Helping students connect the macroscopic level to the molecular level. *Journal of Food Science Education*, 20(4), 166–177. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4329.12232>

Shultz, G. V., & Stears, M. (1996). Using manipulatives to teach the law of conservation of matter. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 73(3), 219–222. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ed073p219>

Swafford, J. A., Flynn, A. B., & Noll, S. (2016). Studying the usage and effectiveness of interactive simulations in stoichiometry instruction. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 93(12), 2020–2027. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.6b00227>

Taber, K. S. (2013). Revisiting the chemistry triplet: drawing upon the nature of chemical knowledge and the psychology of learning to inform chemistry education. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 14(2), 156–168. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3RP00012E>

Talanquer, V. (2011). Macro, submicro, and symbolic: The many faces of the chemistry “triplet.” *International Journal of Science Education*, 33(2), 179–195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500690903386435>

Taskin, V., & Bernholt, S. (2014). Prospective pedagogy for teaching chemical bonding for smart and sustainable learning. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 15(4), 435–446. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4RP00059E>

Verangel, G. V., & Prudente, M. S. (2022). Students' conceptual understanding and confidence on balancing chemical equations using particulate drawings. *The Normal Lights*, 16(1), 197–221. <https://doi.org/10.56278/tnl.v16i1.1717>

Wu, H. K., Krajcik, J., & Soloway, E. (2000). Promoting conceptual understanding of chemical representations: Students' use of a visualization tool in the classroom. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 37(7), 720–742. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1098-2736\(200009\)37:7](https://doi.org/10.1002/1098-2736(200009)37:7)

Yavuz, S., Büyükeksi, C., & Çolakoğlu, Ö. M. (2020). Effects of 3D applications in organic chemistry lessons on students' spatial ability. *Online Science Education Journal*, 5(1), 1–8. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/1159603>

Appendixes

Appendix 1: Balancing Chemical Equations Perception Questionnaire (BCEPQ)

s/n	Statement
1	Chemical equations positively impact society
2	Useful for solving everyday life problems
3	Every chemistry student should know how to balance equations
4	Only chemists need to know how to balance equations (R)
5	Balancing chemical equations is interesting
6	Balancing chemical equations is boring (R)
7	I don't like balancing chemical equations (R)

8	I cannot do chemistry (R)
9	I do not have enough math background to do chemistry (R)
10	Balancing equations is too difficult (R)
11	You need a “scientific mind” to do well in chemistry (R)
12	I get anxious thinking about balancing equations (R)
13	Balancing equations scares me (R)
14	I am nervous when balancing equations (R)
15	Chemistry is mainly for males (R)
16	Males do better than females in balancing equations (R)
17	Balancing equations is easier for males (R)
18	Balancing equations is more difficult for females (R)

Scoring: Strongly agree (5), Agree (4), Neutral (3), Disagree (2), Strongly disagree (1); Negatively worded items (R) are reverse-scored.

Appendix 2: Balancing Chemical Equations Concept Test (BCECT) [40 marks]

Demographic Information

Sex:

Male Female

Age:

12–15 16–20 21–25 26–30

Form/Class: _____

SECTION A: Conceptual Understanding

Answer all questions.

- What are chemical equations?
.....
- Explain the term *balanced chemical equation*.
.....
- Tabulate at least two (2) symbols commonly used in chemical equations and state their meanings.
.....
- Differentiate between reactants and products in a chemical equation.
.....
- State the fundamental principle that governs the balancing of chemical equations.
.....
- Which of the following is the correctly balanced equation for the reaction:
 $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 \rightarrow \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
A. $\text{HNO}_3 + 2\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 \rightarrow \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
B. $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 \rightarrow \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

- C. $2\text{HNO}_3 + \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 \rightarrow \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- D. $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 \rightarrow \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
7. Which of the following is the correctly balanced equation for the reaction:
 $\text{HCl} + \text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaCl}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$
- A. $2\text{HCl} + \text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaCl}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$
- B. $\text{HCl} + 2\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow 2\text{CaCl}_2 + 4\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$
- C. $\text{HCl} + \text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaCl}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$
- D. $\text{HCl} + \text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaCl} + \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{CO}_2$
8. Which of the following is the correctly balanced equation for the reaction:
 $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{NaHCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$
- A. $2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 2\text{NaHCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{CO}_2$
- B. $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{NaHCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$
- C. $2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 2\text{NaHCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}_2$
- D. $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + 2\text{NaHCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{CO}_2$
9. Which of the following is the correctly balanced equation for the reaction:
 $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- A. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6 + 3\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 6\text{CO}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- B. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6 + 6\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 6\text{CO}_2 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- C. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6 + 8\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 6\text{CO}_2 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- D. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 3\text{CO}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$
10. Which of the following is the correctly balanced equation for the reaction:
 $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2$
- A. $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{O}_2$
- B. $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2$
- C. $2\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2$
- D. $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2$

SECTION B: Procedural Skills

Balance the following chemical equations.

- $\text{CH}_4 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- $\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{NH}_3$
- $\text{C} + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4$
- $\text{H}_2 + \text{Br}_2 \rightarrow \text{HBr}$
- $\text{NaOH} + \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \rightarrow \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_6 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$

7. $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2 \rightarrow \text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
8. $\text{Mg} + \text{HCl} \rightarrow \text{MgCl}_2 + \text{H}_2$
9. $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl} + \text{NaOH} \rightarrow \text{NaCl} + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NH}_3$
10. $\text{P}_4\text{O}_{10} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$

